

A QUANTITATIVE INVESTIGATION ON THE THERMOELASTIC EFFECT OF CFRP LAMINATES

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SUMMARY

The thermoelastic effect on CFRP laminates with various lay-ups is investigated. A thick low crimp unidirectional fabric reinforcement is adopted. The measured thermoelastic signal is compared with predictions from two analytical models based on the meso-mechanical bulk properties of the lamina and on assuming a *strain witness* behaviour of the surface resin rich layer.

Keywords: Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastics, Laminates Theory, Thermoelastic Stress Analysis.

INTRODUCTION

The Thermoelastic Effect describes the reversible temperature changes arising in solid matter as a consequence of an elastic strain induced volume change. The combination of thermodynamic laws and elastic constitutive behaviour can provide analytical models of the Thermoelastic Effect [1]. In the particular case of a linear elastic behaviour and adiabatic transformation, linear relationships are obtained which correlate the temperature change to stress or strain components [1,2]., Thermoelastic Stress Analysis (TSA) is the name of the general approach based on such relationships, which derives information about the stress field of dynamically loaded components from measuring the amplitude of the thermoelastic effect induced temperature changes. High resolution IR cameras are generally employed to perform full field non-contact measurements of the temperature changes occurring on a component surface [3].

Application of quantitative TSA to fibre reinforced plastic composites has been traditionally based on formulations of the thermoelastic effect laws which consider the material as homogeneous and exhibiting a linear elastic orthotropic behaviour. A sufficiently general expression based on these assumptions is established as [2]:

$$S = K_{IR} \cdot \Delta T = -K_{IR} \cdot \frac{T_o}{c \cdot \rho} \cdot C_{iikk} \cdot \alpha_{kk} \cdot \Delta \varepsilon_{ii} \quad (i,k=L,T,Z) \quad (1)$$

where ΔT is the temperature change, T_o the absolute temperature of the component, ρ and c_ε the bulk density and the specific heat at constant volume of the homogenised material, C the stiffness tensor, α the coefficient of thermal expansions (CTE) tensor and $\Delta \varepsilon$ the change in the elastic strain tensor induced by cyclic loads. The i,k subscripts

indicate the orthotropic principal material axes with L aligned with the fibres. The thermoelastic signal acquired by the thermocamera, S , is proportional to the thermoelastic effect induced temperature change through a coefficient K_{IR} which is function of the radiometric response of the IR sensor, the camera signal processing settings and the material surface emissivity. By solving a simplified model of the heat exchange between fibres and matrix at the microscale level, Wong [4] provided a justification for the adoption of a homogenised bulk model of the material at the mesoscale level. The adoption of eq. (1) will hereinafter referred to as *bulk model* (BM). The thermoelastic signal is collected on the surface of the component where resin rich zones are usually found. This surface resin rich layer is normally developed during the manufacturing stage as a result of the resin entrapped between the mould surface and the outer prepreg or fabric reinforcement layer. The thickness of this resin layer can range from few tens to few hundreds microns [5-8], and can also vary significantly with the waviness or texture of the fabric employed. The presence of this resin rich layer is not considered in the homogeneous material model, although some authors have detected its influence on the thermoelastic signal [5-9]. Test results collected with different surface resin layer thicknesses and at various loading frequencies have provided hints that the thermoelastic signal measured on the surface is probably generated by the resin layer and to a less extent by the inner fibre reinforced material [5,6]. Assuming that the surface resin layer is a strain witness of the laminate, and treating the resin as an isotropic material, it has been possible to establish alternative analytical relationships for the thermoelastic signal measured on symmetric FRP laminates under in-plane loading, e.g. [8]:

$$S = -K_{IR} \cdot T_o \cdot \frac{\alpha_r}{c_r \cdot \rho_r} \cdot \frac{E_r}{1 - \nu_r} \cdot \Delta \varepsilon_{ii} \quad (2)$$

where subscript r refers to resin properties, E is the Young's modulus and ν the Poisson's coefficient. The validation of the assumptions which lead to eq. (2), hereinafter referred to as *Strain Witness* model (SW), would bring two main advantages in quantitative TSA: the first consists in the possibility to correctly predict the influence of the surface resin layer; the second is the possibility to perform an easier calibration procedure. In fact Eq. (2) suggests the possibility to use a single calibration sample with bonded strain gauges to correlate the signal with measured strain components. Some recent works have tested the SW and BM models focusing on GRP specimens, collecting various experimental evidences in favour of the SW model [7-11].

In the present work experimental and analytical results are presented where the SW and BM models are employed on CFRP laminates. The small value of the longitudinal CTE of a CFRP lamina is recognised to play an important role on the nature of the thermoelastic signal collected on the laminate surface. The investigation performed also exploits the influence of different laminate lay-ups in order to identify configurations which can potentially give rise to markedly different thermoelastic signal predictions between the BM and the SW models [10].

THEORETICAL MODELS OF THE THERMOELASTIC SIGNAL

Equations (2,3) employ strain components. Since linear elastic behaviour is considered in the theory of the Thermoelastic Effect, the generalised Hooke's law, sometimes

referred to as the Duhamel-Neumann's equation, can be used to obtain a stress formulation equivalent to eqs. (2,3). It is useful to derive the stress formulation referring to the stress components along the principal material axes of the outer lamina. Two linear relationships are then obtained for the BM and SW models [7]:

$$S_{BM} = -K_{IR} \cdot A_1 \cdot [\Delta\sigma_{LL} + A_2 \cdot \Delta\sigma_{TT}] \quad (3)$$

$$S_{SW} = -K_{IR} \cdot K_r \cdot B_1 \cdot (\Delta\sigma_{LL} + B_2 \cdot \Delta\sigma_{TT}) \quad (4)$$

where coefficients are defined in table 2. It is interesting to observe that the influence of the transverse stress component σ_{TT} of the outer lamina is enhanced by a factor which is found to be the CTEs ratio for the BM model and proportional to the Young's modules ratio E_L/E_T for the SW model. The two coefficients can differ significantly in the case of a CFRP lamina due to the very low value of α_{LL} . This can sometimes assume also net negative values, with the contribution of σ_{TT} becoming subtractive instead of additive. For the case of GRPs it has been shown that A_1 and $K_r \cdot B_1$ generally have similar values [10,11], so a lamina with a predominant longitudinal stress component σ_{LL} will develop a thermoelastic signal that is predicted reasonably well by both the BM and SW models. Since the objective of the present study is to evaluate the prediction capabilities of the two BM and SW analytical models, it is convenient to seek situations where the outer lamina presents a non negligible transverse stress component so that the difference in the two coefficients A_2 and B_2 would be such to determine a significant difference also in the values of S_{BM} and S_{SW} . If unidirectional tensile specimens are considered, a transverse stress component in the outer lamina can be introduced by misaligning inner laminas with respect to the loading axis, i.e. by considering lay-up stacking sequences different from $[0]_n$.

Table 1: Definition of thermoelastic coefficients shown in eqs. (3,4).

$K_r = \frac{T_o}{c_r \cdot \rho_r} \cdot \alpha_r$	$A_1 = \frac{T_o}{c \cdot \rho} \cdot \alpha_{LL}; \quad A_2 = \frac{\alpha_{TT}}{\alpha_{LL}}$	$B_1 = \frac{E^r}{E_L} \frac{(1 - \nu_{LT})}{(1 - \nu_r)}; \quad B_2 = \frac{E_L(1 - \nu_{TL})}{E_T(1 - \nu_{LT})}$
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Analytical predictions for varying lay-up

A Matlab routine using the classic laminates theory to calculate stresses on the laminate outer lamina has been implemented to simulate the BM and SW models. Unidirectional loaded tensile samples with three symmetric lay-up configurations have been considered in particular: $[(0, \pm\vartheta, 0)]_s$, $[(0, \pm\vartheta, 0_{1.5})]_s$, $[(\vartheta, 0)_2, \vartheta_{0.5}]_s$ (hereinafter referred to as lay-up 1,2 and 3). The thermoelastic signal is predicted under identical axial load, and at values of ϑ ranging between 0° - 90° . In order to eliminate the need to evaluate the thermoelastic coefficients K_{IR} , K_r and A_1 , which depend on various physical material and instrumentation parameters, normalised values of the thermoelastic signal are calculated. These can be directly compared to normalised experimental values without any need for calibration. The normalising factor proposed for each lay-up configuration is the value of the thermoelastic signal corresponding to the lay-up at $\vartheta=0^\circ$, i.e. the unidirectional tensile sample where fibres are aligned with the load. An analytical representation of the normalised thermoelastic signal can be written as:

$$\left(\frac{S_\vartheta}{S_0}\right)_{BM} = \frac{-K_{IR} \cdot A_1 [\Delta\sigma_{LL}(\vartheta^\circ) + A_2 \cdot \Delta\sigma_{TT}(\vartheta^\circ)]}{-K_{IR} \cdot A_1 \cdot \Delta\sigma_{LL}(0^\circ)} = \frac{[\Delta\sigma_{LL}(\vartheta^\circ) + A_2 \cdot \Delta\sigma_{TT}(\vartheta^\circ)]}{\Delta\sigma_{LL}(0^\circ)} \quad (5)$$

$$\left(\frac{S_\vartheta}{S_0}\right)_{SW} = \frac{-K_{IR} \cdot K_r \cdot B_1 [\Delta\sigma_{LL}(\vartheta^\circ) + B_2 \cdot \Delta\sigma_{TT}(\vartheta^\circ)]}{-K_{IR} \cdot K_r \cdot B_1 \cdot \Delta\sigma_{LL}(0^\circ)} = \frac{[\Delta\sigma_{LL}(\vartheta^\circ) + B_2 \cdot \Delta\sigma_{TT}(\vartheta^\circ)]}{\Delta\sigma_{LL}(0^\circ)} \quad (6)$$

The stress functions in eqs. (5) and (6) can be calculated with the classic laminate theory once the lamina elastic constants and CTEs are provided. In this study in-house manufactured CFRP laminates are analysed in the experimental activity (see next section for further details). The lamina orthotropic elastic constants have been measured and used for the analytical simulation. The CTEs of the manufactured samples have not been measured or calculated. Range values from the literature have been considered which are thought to include the CTEs of the analysed material [12]. In particular, as discussed in the next section, the manufactured samples have a fibre volume fraction V_f included between 40% and 50%. In such range it is plausible to assume that the values of the CTEs range between $-1 \mu\text{K}^{-1} \leq \alpha_L \leq 1 \mu\text{K}^{-1}$ and $20 \mu\text{K}^{-1} \leq \alpha_T \leq 50 \mu\text{K}^{-1}$. Figure 1 shows the normalised thermoelastic signal versus ϑ for two lay-up configurations and a choice of CTEs. It is seen that a maximum difference between the BM and SW predictions lies between $25^\circ \leq \vartheta \leq 30^\circ$ for lay-up 2 and at $\vartheta = 90^\circ$ for lay-up 3.

Figure 1: Various predictions of the normalised thermoelastic signal for lay-up 2 $[(0, \pm\vartheta, 0_{1.5})_s]$ and 3 $[(\vartheta, 0)_2, \vartheta_{0.5}]_s$. Lamina elastic properties used are $E_L=172.5$ GPa, $E_T=5.25$ GPa, $G_{LT}=2.7$ GPa, $\nu_{LT}=0.27$.

Figure 2 shows the normalised thermoelastic signal at $\vartheta = 30^\circ$ for lay-up 2 and $\vartheta = 90^\circ$ for lay-up 3 with various CTEs combinations.

Figure 2: Absolute value of the normalised thermoelastic signal maximum for varying CTEs.

EXPERIMENTAL ACTIVITY

Specimen preparation and characterisation

A number of panels with different lay-ups have been manufactured using the same raw materials and processing procedure. The technique used was hand lay-up. Patches of differently oriented dry fabric reinforcement were cut and stacked up according to the lay-up sequence, with each layer manually impregnated by means of hand rollers. A good surface finish, flatness and material consolidation was obtained by preparing the laminates between two glass plates, with a mylar releasing film placed at the mould-laminate interface, and weights resting on top of the mould during the curing time. The reinforcement consisted of a 400 gsm non-crimped unidirectional fabric SikaWrap®-400C Mid Mod NW, and a low viscosity epoxy resin system was used which required room temperature curing followed by a thermal post-curing at 60 degrees for 8 hours.

The fabric was chosen such to have high areal weight, and hence a relatively high thickness. This allowed to reduce stress gradients along the laminate thickness, and so reduce the temperature gradients determined by the thermoelastic effect. In fact these can be very steep (e.g. when thin prepreg layers are used), and make it difficult to achieve adiabatic conditions at loading frequencies below 20-30 Hz [4,5]. The fabric selected is also such to have a low-crimp or waviness of fibre bundles, which are held together through thin thermowelded thermoplastic threads (see fig. 3a). This arrangement is believed to favour a more uniform surface resin layer thickness over the areas not crossed by the thermoplastic threads. A summary of all prepared and tested specimens is shown in table 2 which also reports the elastic constants measured for the manufactured laminates. Young's modules and the Poisson's coefficient were measured on unidirectional tensile samples according to ASTM D3039 standard guidelines. In particular the samples and the testing equipment used for characterisation were carefully

checked against unacceptable spurious bending effects, and an averaging extensometer was used in combination with electrical strain gauges. Each specimen measure was repeated six times. The coefficient of variation next to each elastic property is calculated from the standard deviation of all measures acquired for specimens grouped on the same line of the table (e.g. for specimens s9,s10 and s11 the coefficient of variation of E_T is calculated over eighteen measures, six for each specimen). The in-plane shear modulus was measured with the *Iosipescu* test described in ASTM D5379. Specimens with the same letter in the column TSA session have been tested with the same thermoelastic equipment set-up, within the same experimental session.

Table 2: summary of manufactured laminates and tested specimen.

Sample ID	Panel ID; Lay-up	E_L [GPa]	E_T [GPa]	ν_{LT}	G_{LT} [GPa]	TSA session
s1,s2	1; [0] ₈	171±3.7 %				a
s3,s4	2; [90] ₈		5.21±4.1%			
s5	2; [90] ₈				2.71±0.4%	
s6,s7	3; [0] ₉	172.3±1.3 %		0.27±1.7%		b
s8	3; [0] ₉	174.3±0.3 %				c
s9,s10,s11	3; [90] ₉		5.48±1.9%			
s12,s13	4; [(0,±25,0)] _s					a
s14,s15	5; [0,±30,0 ₃ ,∓30,0]					b
s16	6; [0,±30,0 ₃ ,∓30,0]					c
s17	7; [(90,0) ₂ ,90,(0,90) ₂]					b
s18	7; [(90,0) ₂ ,90,(0,90) ₂]					c

The fibre volume fraction was obtained by weighting all cut samples and working out the equivalent fibre weight, based on the measured total surface area of samples and number of layers. This calculation is affected by the uncertainty in the dry fabric areal weight, reported by the fabric supplier as 400±5% gsm. Considering three values of fabric weight: 380-400-420 gsm, the equivalent fibre volume fraction calculated from all samples was 45-47.5-50%, with a standard deviation of about 1.2%, similar for each of the three values. This procedure for the evaluation of the V_f does not account for voids content. The small standard deviation of measured V_f and the manufacturing procedure adopted, identical for all samples, provide some confidence in assuming that all manufactured samples have similar values of V_f , and that these are likely included between 40-50%. This limitation is important in order to make reasonable assumptions on the range of CTE values that can be attributed to the material [12].

It was not possible to evaluate all elastic constants from each manufactured panel. It is shown though that E_L from panels 1 and 3, and E_T from panels 2 and 3 have very close values. Furthermore the calculated values of V_f from all panels were very close. In light of this the following set of elastic constants was assumed for the material type analysed in this work: $E_L=172.5$ GPa, $E_T=5.25$ GPa, $\nu_{LT}=0.27$, $G_{LT}=2.7$ GPa. These constants

have been used in the Matlab routines (see fig. 1). It is also meaningful to report that the analytical predictions in figures 1 and 2 do not vary significantly when the above elastic constants change within $\pm 10\%$ of the reported values.

Measurement of the thermoelastic signal

The thermoelastic signal was acquired by means of a DeltaTherm 1560 IR camera supplied by Stress Photonics Inc. All samples were tested in load control on a servohydraulic testing machine with sinusoidal loads cycling between 2-18 kN. Each sample was tested at various load frequencies ranging between 3 Hz and 15 Hz. A careful tuning of the PID parameters of the servohydraulic machine was carried out during each specimen test, to ensure an equal peak to peak load to be applied on all samples and for all frequencies. All samples had nominal width and length of about 25 mm and 250 mm, and the upper half of each sample was painted with a matt black paint. It was observed that the signal acquired on the painted area had lower noise from environment reflection, and the quantitative data presented in this work are then all collected from the painted surface area.

An example of the appearance of the thermoelastic signal acquired is reported in fig. 3. It can be noticed that a strong perturbation is produced by the thermoplastic threads. In order to extrapolate an average value of the thermoelastic signal the DeltaTherm maps were imported in Matlab and the signal collected from smaller square areas not crossing the thermoelastic threads (see for instance fig. 3b).

Figure 3: a) image of the dry reinforcement fabric with the diagonal thermoplastic threads; b) Map of the thermoelastic signal (R component) from sample s8; the square boxes in dash line bound the areas where the signal was collected and averaged. c) Thermoelastic signal from s16; d) Thermoelastic signal from s18.

Quantitative analysis of the thermoelastic signal

For each specimen the thermoelastic signal was acquired sequentially at frequencies of 5-10-15 Hz (for samples tested during the TSA session b) or 3-5-8-10-12-15 Hz (for all other samples). This sequence was repeated twice so that two measures for each

frequency value and specimen were obtained, showing a very good repeatability. It was observed also that the thermoelastic signal did not show any meaningful variation with frequency. Some plots of the thermoelastic signal versus frequency are shown in fig. 4.

Figure 4: Thermoelastic signal in uncalibrated DeltaTherm units versus load frequency from the TSA session b (left) and from the TSA session c (right).

Normalised values of the thermoelastic signal are summarised in table 3, with the data obtained from experiments reported in column 2. It is first of all observed that normalised data are derived only among samples tested in the same TSA session, in order to ensure the same thermocamera radiometric setting and environmental conditions. Layup 2 differ from layup 1 only for the presence of one more 0° lamina in the middle. This produces only a small difference in the theoretical values of the normalised signal. It is then meaningful to notice that the experimental values of $|s_{12}/s_1|$, $|s_{14}/s_6|$ and $|s_{16}/s_8|$ are all very close, regardless of the slight differences in layup, and regardless that data were collected in different TSA sessions. This confirms that the normalised thermoelastic signal is indeed mainly dependent on the layup of the specimens considered.

Table 3: summary of experimental values and theoretical predictions of the absolute normalised thermoelastic signals from different sample lay-ups.

Absolute Normalised Thermoelastic Signal	TSA session	Exp	SW	BM	
				$\alpha_L = -0.25 \mu\text{K}^{-1}$ $\alpha_T = 30 \mu\text{K}^{-1}$	$\alpha_L = 0.25 \mu\text{K}^{-1}$ $\alpha_T = 30 \mu\text{K}^{-1}$
$ s_{12}/s_1 $; $ s_{13}/s_2 $	a	5.7	1.25	8.44	5.68
$ s_{14}/s_6 $; $ s_{15}/s_7 $	b	5.23	0.97	7.95	5.06
$ s_{17}/s_6 $	c	8.87	2.92	7.9	7.87
$ s_{16}/s_8 $	c	5.76	0.97	7.95	5.06
$ s_{18}/s_8 $	b	8.07	2.92	7.9	7.87
$ s_{18}/s_{16} $	c	1.4	3.01	0.99	1.55

When theoretical predictions of the normalised thermoelastic signal are considered (see fig. 1), it is found that these can also have negative values, obtained when S_{90° and S_{0° have opposite signs. It is important to observe that the lock-in filtering operation performed by DeltaTherm is not able to assess the sign of the thermoelastic signal which can be arbitrarily changed according with the phase shift set between the reference signal and the thermographic signal. A practical consequence is that only absolute values of the thermoelastic signal are obtained from DeltaTherm, and hence only positive normalised thermoelastic signal data can be computed from the experimental results. In light of this, the absolute values of the analytically predicted normalised thermoelastic signals are also considered in fig. 2 and table 3.

CONCLUSIONS

In general all the experimental values of the normalised thermoelastic signal found in this work, differ quite significantly from the SW predictions. Since an exact knowledge of the CTEs for the tested material is unknown, it is not rigorous to conclude that the BM model predictions are in better agreement. The normalised SW predictions depend only on the elastic properties of the lamina (see eq. 6), which have been measured with sufficient accuracy, at least in the authors' opinion. So it is doubtful that the significant difference found between the SW predictions and the experimental data can be severely questioned on the basis of a more accurate material characterisation required. Also the acquisition of the thermoelastic signal was treated with some accuracy, by repeating measurements, performing different TSA sessions, and analysing different lay-ups.

It is observed that the signal measured from the unidirectional samples is rather low, and generally quite heavily affected by random noise. In this respect it is probably not ideal the choice to use the $[0]_n$ layup configuration as normalising factor. This can be taken as a recommendation for the future if the approach proposed in this work is to be followed by further analyses. Data from the TSA session c allow to derive also a normalised thermoelastic signal using two non unidirectional lay-ups. In particular this is possible with samples s18 (having layup type 3) and s16 (having layup type 2). For both samples the thermoelastic signal was almost an order of magnitude higher than that from the unidirectional samples. Again it is found that the value of $|s18/s16|$ is significantly lower than the SW prediction, confirming the previous results.

Columns five and six from table 3 report two examples of the BM prediction for two different choices of CTEs. The values of column six in particular seem to match very well the experimental values. The value of α_{LL} used in this case is positive. It is interesting to observe that a positive net value for α_{LL} is also predicted in [6] for CFRP laminas with $V_f < 50\%$, and in Wong [4] and Dunn [5] based on the micromechanical thermoelastic approach presented in their works.

It is believed that the net value of α_{LL} in CFRPs is very much influenced by the extent of the surface resin rich layer thickness. Unfortunately it has not been possible to attempt any experimental evaluation of this parameter in this work. It is believed though that the hand lay-up manufacturing technique employed in this work would give rise to consistent amounts of surface resin, due to the lack of high pressure consolidation of the packed laminate during the curing stage. From these considerations a final

hypothesis can be drawn that the material tested in this work had a surface resin rich layer thick enough to develop a positive net value of α_{LL} , but not thick enough to generate a complete “strain witness” behaviour.

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